

The Impact of Tax Incentives on Revenue Generation

Obehi Omena Igbinoba

University of Benin

omena.igbinoba@uniben.edu

Fredrick Uyiosa Osazuwa

University of Benin

uyifredrick@gmail.com

Abstract

This study was carried out to examine the impact of tax incentives on revenue generation in Nigeria. The study employed the ordinary least squares regression technique to examine the impact. Data for the study was gathered from responses by various respondents for the study. The findings showed that Investment Allowance and Tax Credit play a positive and significant role in revenue generation; Tax Holiday has a weak impact; and Export Exemption does not significantly influence revenue generation. Based on the findings, it was therefore recommended that since Investment Allowance is the most significant factor influencing revenue generation, policymakers should consider expanding or modifying this incentive to encourage more investment and economic growth. In addition, governments should ensure that tax credit policies remain attractive and effective in stimulating economic activities. Also given the marginal significance of Tax Holiday, policymakers should assess whether this incentive is effectively promoting business growth or if adjustments are needed to make it more impactful. It was also recommended that since export exemption was found to be non-statistically significant, it may not be an effective tool for increasing revenue generation. Instead, resources should be redirected towards more impactful tax incentives.

Keywords: Investment Allowance, Tax Credit, Tax Holiday, Revenue generation

JEL Classification: H25, H20, H32

1. Introduction

Nigeria's government has recognized the need to diversify its economy and reduce its reliance on oil exports. The government has implemented various economic policies and reforms to achieve this, including the use of tax incentives to stimulate investment, promote industrialization, and enhance revenue generation. Augustin et al. (2023) state that revenue generation refers to the process by which a business or organization earns money through the sale of goods, services, or other sources of income. It involves various strategies and activities aimed at increasing the company's income. Zolt (2023) define revenue generation as the sustainability and growth of any business, as it directly impacts profitability. The study further states that revenue generation refers to the ways in which governments or businesses generate

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

income through taxation or tax-related policies. Revenue generation is significantly increased when there is effective implementation of tax incentives, as these incentives play a critical role in fostering investment, driving business expansion, and stimulating economic activity (Millot et al., 2020).

Tax incentives on the other hand encourage companies to reinvest their profits into growth initiatives by reducing the financial burden on businesses, create jobs, and enhance productivity. According to Okeke et al. (2018), tax incentives are fiscal policies used by the government to encourage specific economic activities, investments, or behaviors by reducing the tax burden on businesses or individuals. There are various forms of tax incentives, such as tax holidays, drawbacks, reliefs, credits, exemptions, and allowances. Furthermore, Okeke et al. (2018) states that the primary goal of tax incentives is to create a more favorable business environment, attract both domestic and foreign investment, and ultimately drive economic growth and development. These tax incentives are categorized into cost-based tax incentives and profit-based tax incentives.

According to Nnubia and Obiora (2018), cost-based tax incentives such as Pioneer Status Incentive (PSI), are those that directly reduce the cost of investment, such as investment allowances, accelerated depreciation, and tax holidays. While profit-based tax incentives, on the other hand, are those that reduce the tax liability on the profits generated by the investment, such as tax credits, reduced tax rates, and tax exemptions (Nnubia & Obiora, 2018). Ugwu et al. (2020) state that the impact of tax incentives on revenue generation is multifaceted, as tax incentives attract new investments, encourage the expansion of existing businesses, and stimulate economic growth through increased productivity and innovation. Governments must balance the potential revenue gains from increased economic activity with the short-term loss in tax revenue due to the incentives (Sebele-Mpofu et al., 2022). Therefore, it is crucial for the Nigerian government to carefully design and implement tax incentive policies, monitor their effectiveness, and ensure that the incentives are aligned with the overall economic development objectives of the country.

The impact of tax incentives on revenue generation, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria, presents a complex and multifaceted issue. According to Olowo et al. (2020), tax incentives are widely used to attract investment, stimulate industrial growth, and promote economic development. Their effectiveness in generating revenue is contingent upon careful design and implementation. However, most businesses in most underdeveloped and developing countries are less motivated to comply with tax regulations, leading to higher rates of tax evasion. Tax evasion undermines the government's ability to collect the necessary revenue. It often forces authorities to spend more resources on enforcement, audits, and legal proceedings to ensure compliance (Okoth, 2023). According to Siyanbola et al. (2017), businesses fail to invest or expand, which stifles economic growth due to the ineffective implementation of tax incentives. Without the economic stimulation that tax incentives provide, the tax base may shrink, leading to lower tax revenues over time as businesses remain stagnant or shift their operations to more favorable tax environments.

Although it is more challenging to encourage the informal sector or new businesses to formalize and join the tax system when there are no effective tax incentives. Many small businesses or startups in underdeveloped and developing countries, including Nigeria remain in the informal economy to avoid the full tax burden (Sebele-Mpofu et al., 2022). This limits the government's ability to broaden the tax base and capture potential revenue from these entities (Oguttu, 2018). Increased administrative efforts to collect taxes without offering incentives lead to higher operational costs for tax authorities, reducing the efficiency of the tax system.

It is pertinent to note that Nigerian governments depend on tax holiday and tax credit incentives to boost their economies through increased investment (Gabriel & Ezekiel, 2019). The revenue losses that result from these incentives create doubt about their ability to improve total revenue collection. The existing empirical research does not provide a clear answer about the fiscal impact of tax incentives which either benefit government revenue or harm it. The system fails to protect against misuse of incentives because it lacks effective monitoring systems and proper incentive distribution methods.

Flowing from the above, the broad objective is to examine the impact of tax incentives on revenue generation in Nigeria. The remaining sections of this study is as follows: section 2. Concept of tax incentive, 2.1-Types of Tax Incentives, 2.2-Revenue Generation, 2.3-Theoretical framework, 2.4-Empirical framework; section 3. Methodology, 4-Data analysis and presentation and 5-Conclusion and recommendation.

2. Concept of Tax Incentive

Taxation is crucial for economic growth, especially in resource-scarce countries. Tax incentives attract new investments and expand existing ones based on a country's development plan (Jahanger, 2021). However, while exemptions encourage investment, they can also shrink the tax base and reduce tax revenue efficiency (Huang & Liu, 2024). Hofman (2018) defines tax incentives as government measures designed to encourage taxpayers to comply with their tax obligations. These measures include policy adjustments that reduce the tax burden on specific industries, groups, or services. They may involve lower tax rates, better dissemination of fiscal information, or even tax exemptions (Imran & Rehman, 2024). Similarly, Hall and Van Reenen (2020) describe tax incentives as deliberate tax reductions aimed at encouraging businesses to invest, produce, employ, export, save, or adopt environmentally friendly practices (González-Rodríguez et al., 2021). Other incentives included Companies Income Tax Relief, which provided capital allowances for investments in machinery and buildings, as well as loss carry-forward provisions. Additionally, Import Duties Relief exempted selected pioneer companies from paying import duties on inputs, while the Approved User Scheme refunded import duties to approved enterprises engaged in export-oriented production (Genschel & Seelkopf, 2016).

2.1. Types of tax incentives

Nigeria offers various tax incentives to encourage investment and business growth. These incentives aim to boost production, job creation, exports, and sales while reducing consumption, imports, and pollution (Peters & Kiabel, 2015).

2.1.1. Pioneer industries relief or tax exemption

This is also known as a tax holiday; it is the most widespread tax incentive in developing countries, including Nigeria. Tax exemption, whole or partial, is tax concession over a period of time, granted by the government to individual and corporate taxpayers. According to Ayua (2007), cited in Soon, Derashid, and Bidin (2020), it simply means a period of exemption from the payment of taxes imposed by the government, and this exemption may be complete or partial. The Industrial Development (Income Tax Relief) Act 1971 repealed the 1958 Act but re-enacted the contents of the latter Act, though with certain major changes. A similar provision is contained in the Industrial Development (Income Tax Relief) Act, which has consolidated the 1971 Act (Vincent, 2021). The period for which a pioneer company is granted tax relief under the 1990 Act is between three and five years, and the period shall begin from the date on which the company commenced production. The period within which this relief is granted is called the pioneer period, and these companies are referred to as pioneer companies. The profits of a pioneer company are exempted from tax during the tax relief period, but where it earns profit from activities other than its pioneer enterprises, it will be liable to tax (Tijjani et al., 2023). However, the Nigeria Tax Act, 2025 has repealed the Industrial Development (Income Tax Relief) Act and replaced it with the Economic Development Tax Incentive Framework. The new framework adopts a more targeted performance-based approach tied to qualifying capital expenditure in priority sectors.

2.1.2. Tax credits

A tax credit is the amount of money taxpayers are permitted to subtract from the income tax liability that they owe to the government (Abdelhakim & Zouaghi, 2022). It is an incentive that allows businesses to subtract a specified amount directly from their total tax liability. Tax credits may be offered for activities that align with government priorities, such as investments in renewable energy, infrastructure development, or research and development (R&D) (Abdelhakim & Zouaghi, 2022).

2.1.3. Export expansion grant (EEG) scheme

This incentive aims to support active exporters; expanding their international businesses. It is a post-shipment incentive designed to encourage Nigerian exporters to expand export volume, value and improve global competitiveness of Nigerian products. According to Bloom et al., (2022), Nigerian exporters get between 5% to 15% of their annual export value, depending on exporters' product category. Successful exporters are paid through the instrument known as Export Credit Certificate (ECC) which is used for settlement of all Federal Government taxes such as company income tax, Value Added Tax, and Withholding Tax.

2.1.4. Investment allowance

Investment allowances are forms of tax relief that are based on the value of expenditures on qualifying investments. These allowances provide tax benefits over and above the depreciation allowed for the asset. A tax allowance is used to reduce the taxable income of the firm (Peters & Kiabel, 2015). Ngure (2018) states that in Nigeria, investment allowances remain a significant tool for stimulating industrial growth, especially in the manufacturing, agriculture, and energy sectors, where capital investments are essential for productivity and innovation. This framework has, however, been significantly changed. The Finance Act 2023 has removed

the Company Income Tax Act provisions on investment allowance, meaning that the incentive is no longer available for new qualifying investments made after the reform took effect; only investments that took place before the reform will continue to benefit from the relief.

2.2. Revenue generation

Government revenue generation is a critical aspect of economic management, ensuring the availability of funds for public services, infrastructure, and national development. Scholars have explored various sources of government revenue, emphasizing taxation, non-tax revenues, borrowing, and earnings from state-owned enterprises (Dai & Chapman, 2022). Taxation remains the most significant means of revenue generation for governments worldwide. According to Chen and Yang (2019), taxes are compulsory payments imposed on individuals and businesses to fund government activities. These include direct taxes such as income tax and corporate tax, as well as indirect taxes like value-added tax (VAT), excise duties, and customs duties. Effective tax administration is essential in ensuring compliance and maximizing revenue collection.

2.3. Theoretical review

This study was anchored on two theories: Optimal Tax Theory and Peacock-Wiseman's Theory.

2.3.1. Optimal tax theory

This theory was propounded by Frank Ramsey in 1927. The theory posits that a tax system should be designed to maximize social welfare subject to a set of constraints. The theory holds that the tax system should be designed in a way that the government is able to generate the revenue needed for public expenditure while minimizing distortions in economic behaviour (Abdulrahman & Kabir, 2017). The standard theory of optimal taxation assumes that the social planner seeks to choose a tax structure that balances two main goals: raising sufficient public revenue and minimizing the distortions that taxation may create in economic decisions such as production, investment, and consumption. As noted in the literature, the social welfare function may be based on individual utilities in society, whether viewed from a utilitarian or redistributive perspective (Nnubia & Obiora, 2018).

A major assumption in tax policy analysis is that taxation affects the choices of firms and individuals (Obafemi et al., 2021). This assumption is sometimes extended to suggest that the economy consists of identical individuals. Thus, taxes should not be imposed in ways that discourage production activities. Tax incentives are often introduced to encourage investment and business expansion in certain sectors of the economy. From the perspective of optimal tax theory, such incentives may be justified if they help reduce the distortionary effects of taxation and stimulate economic activities that broaden tax revenue over time.

2.3.2. Peacock Wiseman's theory

This theory, propounded in the United Kingdom between 1898 and 1995, suggests that while the government increases spending, citizens are reluctant to pay taxes. This reluctance stems from a lack of trust in how tax revenue is utilized. The theory proposes that the government should meet public expectations to encourage tax compliance. It focuses on the displacement

effect of taxation (Ndu, 2018). The displacement effect occurs when tax revenue meant for socio-economic development is redirected toward social disturbances, war, or natural disasters. Such diversions reduce funding for essential infrastructure and services that would benefit citizens (Obafemi et al., 2021). The theory argues that tax revenue should be used for its intended purpose to directly benefit citizens, thereby motivating them to pay taxes. It supports tax collection but emphasizes proper utilization.

2.4. Empirical review

Abiola and Asiweh (2012) cited in Soon et al. (2021) highlight the role of Lagos State in government revenue generation, noting its significant achievement in financial independence through internally generated revenue. Tax incentives play a crucial role in enhancing revenue generation by encouraging businesses to comply with tax obligations and invest in key sectors of the economy. Manir and Zubairu (2026) study investigates the influence of tax incentives on revenue production by the Nigeria Revenue Service (NRS), using a yearly dataset from 1990 to 2023 and a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) for analysis. The findings show a significant relationship between tax incentives, inflation, and foreign direct investment over various time periods. In the long term, the tax incentive yearly allowance has little influence on revenue, however the tax incentive investment allowance has a considerable negative impact, implying that it reduces revenue creation.

The study of Abiodun (2020) examined how tax collection and incentives affect economic growth in Nigeria. The Central Bank of Nigeria and the Federal Inland Revenue Service provided yearly statistics from 2010 to 2018. A multiple regression model was utilised, with tax revenue proxied by real total tax collected, tax incentives proxied by foreign direct investment equity, and foreign direct investment other capital as independent variables.

The dependent variable was real GDP, which served as a proxy for economic growth. The data was examined for heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, and serial correlation to determine the model's robustness. The results showed that there is a negative but small association between tax revenue and economic growth. The data also demonstrated a negative but statistically insignificant link between foreign direct investment equity and economic growth. While empirical evidence confirms a negative and substantial link between foreign direct investment, other capital, and economic growth.

Folayan and Adeniyi (2018) examine the impact of tax evasion on revenue generation in Nigeria using both qualitative and quantitative data, with the latter sourced from Oyo State's internally generated revenue. Their findings reveal that tax evasion negatively affects revenue generation, emphasizing the need for well-structured tax incentives to promote compliance, increase tax revenue, and support sustainable economic growth. Adefeso (2018) examines how tax policies influence a country's growth rate, using cross-country data from 1970-1997. Their findings show that statutory corporate tax rates are significantly negatively correlated with economic growth rates across countries, even when controlling for other factors affecting growth and tax variables. Olotu (2012) highlights the efforts of various state governors, including Governor Okorocha (Imo State), former Governor Oshiomole (Edo State), former Governor Fashola (Lagos State), and former Governor Amaechi (Rivers State), in harnessing tax revenues to drive development in their respective states.

Supriyati (2021) explored the relationship between Company Income Tax and Nigeria's economic development. Using Chi-square and Multiple Linear Regression analysis, they concluded that there is a significant relationship between company income tax and economic development. However, tax evasion and avoidance were identified as major obstacles to effective revenue generation. Animasaun (2017) investigated the link between tax administration and Ogun State's revenue generation. Through descriptive and inferential statistics, the study found no significant connection between tax administration and revenue generation in Ogun State during the period under review.

Tilahun (2019) examined the impact of tax reforms on Nigeria's economic growth using descriptive statistics and econometric analysis. Their findings indicate that tax reforms positively and significantly influence economic growth. They disaggregated tax revenue into components such as excise duties, personal income tax, petroleum profit tax, companies' income tax, value-added tax, and education tax, concluding that these revenue sources contribute positively to the economy. To address challenges in tax management, their study analyzed the relationship between various tax revenues and overall revenue generation in Nigeria, highlighting the importance of effective tax policies in sustaining economic growth.

The study of Soetan (2017) examined the connection between tax administration and its revenue generation in Nigeria. The study used a quantitative survey while descriptive and regression methods were used. It was found that in the study, tax administration revealed a significant impact on revenue generation during the study period.

Aladejebi (2018) investigated the degree of tax compliance among owners of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. Findings showed that female SME owners are more tax compliant than their male counterparts. In a cross-country study on the contribution of tax incentives towards FDI inflow into Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa by Ugwu (2018), it was discovered that there is a positive association between tax incentives and FDI and that FDI had no significant effect on the exports of Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa.

Ngure (2018) assessed tax incentives and their effect on the performance of selected manufacturing firms in Kenya. The study findings revealed that corporate income tax, capital allowance incentives, custom duty incentives, and excise tax incentives have a direct and significant effect on the performance of the firms. Tapang et al. (2018) focused on the effect of tax incentives on foreign direct investment in the petroleum industry in Nigeria. The findings revealed that tax incentives proxied by investment tax allowances, non-productive rent, and capital allowances have a significant effect on foreign direct investment.

Adefeso (2018) analyzed the impact of corporate tax policy on the performance of 54 randomly selected non-financial listed companies in Nigeria from 1990 to 2002. Using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), the study unexpectedly found a positive relationship between corporate tax policy and the output performance of quoted manufacturing firms. Similarly, Twesige and Gasheja (2019) examined the effect of tax incentives on the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Rwanda, focusing on SMEs in Nyarugenge. The study concluded that tax incentives play a crucial role in ensuring the sustainable growth of SMEs.

Based on the review, the study therefore hypothesize that tax incentive has a significant impact on revenue generation

3. Methodology

3.1 Research design

This study employed a survey research design in addition to an ex-post facto (exploratory non-experimental) research strategy. With the knowledge that there has been a past manifestation of the link among the variables, this study used these research designs to define the statistical correlation.

The justification for this research design is that it facilitates an in-depth examination of the ways in which these pre-existing conditions impact the dependent variable (Revenue generation), Consequently, these integrated designs are warranted in offering both depth and temporal context to the interplay among the study variables, enhancing a more precise and sophisticated comprehension of the phenomena.

3.2. Population and sample size of the study

This study's population consist of corporate entities benefiting from tax incentives, including manufacturing firms and SMEs, as well as tax professionals, policymakers, and financial analysts involved in tax administration and revenue generation. The total respondents for this study is made up of a hundred person which were purposively selected across the various corporate entities and tax professionals respectively.

3.3. Source of data

This study used primary data gathered from the various respondents for the analysis.

3.4. Model specification and analysis

The model for this study was adapted from the study of Adereti (2011). The model was first stated in its functional form as

$$REVGEN = F(TAXHOL, TAXCRDIT, EXPOTEX, INVESTALW).....(1)$$

- REVGEN= Revenue generation
- TAXHOLI=Tax Holidays
- TAXCRDIT= tax credit
- EXPOTEX= export expansion grant
- INVESTALW= investment allowance

The model is further stated in its econometric form as

$$REVGEN = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TAXHOL_i + \beta_2 TAXCRDIT_i + \beta_3 EXPOTEX_i + \beta_4 INVESTALW_i + \mu_i... (2)$$

3.5. Method of analysis

In order to analyse the data, descriptive statistics, ordinary least squares, and Pearson correlation was used. For the purpose of visualising patterns and correlations between data, descriptive statistics like standard deviation and mean was used in the study. To find out how well the dependent and independent variables are related, the study utilised the Pearson correlation. The impact of each variable on the others will be examined using ordinary least squares (OLS) regression. The unbiased, efficient, and consistently-produced estimates of the OLS make it one of the finest linear unbiased estimators (Iyoha, 2004).

3.6. Diagnostic tests

In order to rule out any potential shortcomings, diagnostic tests were run prior to conducting the study. Some of the diagnostic procedures performed included

3.6.1. Test for normality

To ensure that the distribution was normal, the Jarque Bera statistics were used. As a result, the variables are regularly distributed, as the histogram graph has a bell-shaped form. Furthermore, the Kurtosis and Skewness of the curve will be considered in order to check for any potential flaws in its form.

3.6.2. Test for multicollinearity

When the variables show collinearity, this will happen. At that point, they continue to exhibit a very close linear relationship. To find out whether the assumption is correct, we utilised the variance inflation factor (VIF). Failure to detect multicollinearity is indicated by a centred variance inflation factor value ranging from 1 to 10.

3.6.3. Test for heteroskedasticity

This constitutes a breach of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) assumption known as homoskedasticity, indicating the presence of multiple variances within the model. When this condition is satisfied, the BLUE properties of OLS are compromised. If the F-statistic and observed R-squared values exceed the predetermined significance level of 5%, it suggests that the assumption of heteroskedasticity is not valid in the model.

3.6.4. Test for autocorrelation

The correlation that happens when parameters are ordered by time or space is represented by this. Serial correlation describes it when ordered by time, while spatial correlation describes it when ordered by space. When the statistical error term shows time-dependent autocorrelation, it is said to have occurred. $U_t = F(U_{t-1})$ indicates the presence of autocorrelation. In order to determine if autocorrelation is present, the study used the Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic. Values below 1.5 and above 2.4 imply autocorrelation.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Results

This section presents the results of the analysis conducted to examine the impact of tax incentives on revenue generation. The data collected was analyzed using multiple regression techniques, with Revenue Generation (RevGen) as the dependent variable and Tax Holiday (TaxHoli), Tax Credit (TaxCrdit), Export Exemption (ExpotEx), and Investment Allowance (InvestAlw) as the independent variables. The findings are discussed in relation to the study's objectives, and the statistical significance of each variable is evaluated. The results are interpreted based on economic and financial implications, highlighting the extent to which tax incentives contribute to revenue generation.

Table 1: Gender distribution

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	53	55.8	55.8	55.8
	Female	42	44.2	44.2	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

The gender distribution of the sample consists of 53 males (55.8%) and 42 females (44.2%), indicating a relatively balanced representation.

Table 2: Age group

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25years	19	20.0	20.0	20.0
	26-35years	18	18.9	18.9	38.9
	36-45years	18	18.9	18.9	57.9
	46-55years	23	24.2	24.2	82.1
	5.00	17	17.9	17.9	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

The age distribution of the sample indicates that respondents are spread across different age groups, with the highest proportion (24.2%) falling within the 46-55 years category. The youngest group, aged 18-25 years, comprises 19 respondents (20.0%), while those aged 26-35 years and 36-45 years each account for 18 respondents (18.9%). An additional category labeled "5.00" includes 17 respondents (17.9%), though this appears to be a possible data entry error. The cumulative percentage confirms that by the time all age groups are considered, the total reaches 100%. This distribution suggests a diverse age representation, with a relatively balanced spread among the different working-age categories, though further clarification of the "5.00" category may be needed for accuracy in analysis.

Table 3: Education Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Secondary School Certificate	24	25.3	25.3	25.3
	Diploma	19	20.0	20.0	45.3
	Bachelor's Degree	13	13.7	13.7	58.9
	Master's Degree	14	14.7	14.7	73.7
	Doctorate (PhD)	25	26.3	26.3	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

The educational qualification distribution of respondents reveals a diverse range of academic backgrounds. The largest proportion, 26.3%, holds a Doctorate (PhD), indicating a strong presence of highly educated individuals. This is followed by those with a Secondary School Certificate, accounting for 25.3% of the sample. Respondents with a Diploma make up 20.0%, while those with a Master's Degree constitute 14.7%, slightly surpassing the 13.7% who hold a Bachelor's Degree. The cumulative percentage shows a progressive increase, reaching 100% as all educational levels are accounted for. This distribution suggests a well-represented mix of

educational qualifications, with a notable concentration at both the secondary school and doctorate levels.

Table 4: Employment Sector

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Government	20	21.1	21.1	21.1
	Private Sector	27	28.4	28.4	49.5
	Acadeia/Research	27	28.4	28.4	77.9
	Self-employed	21	22.1	22.1	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

The employment sector distribution shows a fairly balanced representation across different sectors. The highest proportion of respondents, 28.4%, are employed in both the Private Sector and Academia/Research, highlighting a strong presence of professionals in these fields. Government employees account for 21.1% of the sample, while self-employed individuals make up 22.1%. The cumulative percentages indicate a steady increase, reaching 100% with all employment categories covered. This distribution suggests a well-diversified workforce, with significant participation from private, academic, and self-employed sectors alongside government employment.

Table 5: Work Experience

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 1 year	23	24.2	24.2	24.2
	1-5years	28	29.5	29.5	53.7
	6-10years	20	21.1	21.1	74.7
	More than 15years	24	25.3	25.3	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

The distribution of work experience among respondents indicates a varied level of professional tenure. The largest group, 29.5%, has between 1 to 5 years of experience, suggesting a significant presence of early-career professionals. Those with less than one year of experience constitute 24.2%, indicating a notable proportion of newcomers to the workforce. Meanwhile, 21.1% of respondents have 6 to 10 years of experience, reflecting a segment of mid-career professionals. The most experienced group, with over 15 years of work experience, accounts for 25.3% of the total sample. This distribution suggests a well-balanced mix of individuals across different career stages, with a considerable representation of both early and highly experienced professionals.

Table 6: Industry of work

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Finance & Banking	17	17.9	17.9	17.9
	Manufacturing	20	21.1	21.1	38.9
	Trade & Commerce	19	20.0	20.0	58.9
	Agriculture	23	24.2	24.2	83.2
	Oil & Gas	16	16.8	16.8	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

The distribution of respondents across various industries highlights the diverse professional backgrounds represented in the study. The largest segment, 24.2%, is engaged in the agriculture sector, suggesting its prominence within the workforce. Manufacturing follows with 21.1%, indicating a significant presence in industrial production. Trade and commerce account for 20.0%, reflecting the importance of business and commercial activities. The finance and banking sector comprises 17.9% of respondents, showing a strong representation of financial professionals. Lastly, the oil and gas industry, with 16.8%, demonstrates its continued relevance, albeit with a slightly lower proportion. This distribution underscores the broad spectrum of industries in which respondents are employed, with a notable balance between primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors.

Table 7: Are you directly involved in taxation or financial planning

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	47	49.5	49.5	49.5
	No	48	50.5	50.5	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

The distribution of respondents based on their direct involvement in taxation or financial planning is nearly evenly split. A total of 47 respondents (49.5%) indicate direct involvement, while 48 respondents (50.5%) are not directly engaged in these areas. This balance suggests that the sample includes both professionals with expertise in taxation and financial planning, as well as individuals from other backgrounds. The representation of both groups ensures a diverse perspective in the study, which may contribute to a more comprehensive analysis of taxation and financial planning-related issues.

Table 8: Have you benefited from any government tax incentives

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	31	32.6	32.6	32.6
	No	26	27.4	27.4	60.0
	Not Sure	38	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

The responses regarding government tax incentives show a varied level of awareness and participation. A total of 31 respondents (32.6%) have benefited from tax incentives, indicating that a portion of the population has successfully accessed government tax relief programs. Meanwhile, 26 respondents (27.4%) reported not receiving any benefits, suggesting potential gaps in accessibility or eligibility. Notably, the largest group, 38 respondents (40.0%), is unsure whether they have benefited, which may reflect a lack of awareness or understanding of tax incentives. This distribution highlights the need for greater awareness and transparency regarding government tax incentives to ensure eligible individuals and businesses can fully take advantage of them.

Table 9: Do you think the current tax system effectively supports revenue generation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	33	34.7	34.7	34.7
	No	29	30.5	30.5	65.3
	Not Sure	33	34.7	34.7	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

The perception of the effectiveness of the current tax system in supporting revenue generation is divided among respondents. An equal proportion of 33 respondents (34.7%) believe the system is effective, while an identical number remain uncertain, indicating a significant level of indecision or lack of clarity on the matter. Meanwhile, 29 respondents (30.5%) do not believe the tax system effectively supports revenue generation, suggesting concerns about its efficiency, structure, or implementation. This distribution highlights the need for further assessment and potential reforms in the tax system to enhance transparency, efficiency, and public confidence in its role in revenue generation.

Table 10: Descriptive statistic

	REVGEN	TAXHOLI	TAXCRDIT	EXPOTEX	INVESTALW
Mean	2.894737	2.884211	3.105263	3.031579	2.873684
Median	3.000000	3.000000	3.000000	3.000000	3.000000
Maximum	5.000000	4.000000	5.000000	4.000000	4.000000
Minimum	1.000000	2.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
Std. Dev.	0.675934	0.666256	0.750513	0.659668	0.639849
Skewness	0.127202	0.131696	-0.324606	-0.256253	-0.376622
Kurtosis	3.434346	2.254194	3.113239	3.044558	3.568382
Jarque-Bera	1.002954	2.476343	1.719102	1.047567	3.524643
Probability	0.605636	0.289914	0.423352	0.592275	0.171646
Sum	275.0000	274.0000	295.0000	288.0000	273.0000
Sum Sq. Dev.	42.94737	41.72632	52.94737	40.90526	38.48421
Observations	95	95	95	95	95

Where:

REVGEN= Revenue generation

TAXHOLI=Tax Holidays

TAXCRDIT= tax credit

EXPOTEX= export expansion grant

INVESTALW= investment allowance

The descriptive statistics in the table 10 provide an overview of the distribution and characteristics of the five variables: Revenue Generation (REVGEN), Tax Holidays (TAXHOLI), Tax Credit (TAXCRDIT), Export Expansion Grant (EXPOTEX), and Investment Allowance (INVESTALW). The mean values for all variables are close to 3, indicating a relatively balanced distribution. TAXCRDIT has the highest mean value (3.105), suggesting a slightly higher tendency for tax credits compared to other incentives, while INVESTALW has the lowest mean (2.873). The median values are all equal to 3, further supporting the observation of a relatively symmetric distribution.

In terms of dispersion, TAXCRDIT exhibits the highest standard deviation (0.750), indicating greater variability among responses, whereas INVESTALW has the lowest standard deviation (0.639), implying a more consistent distribution. The skewness values show that REVGGEN and TAXHOLI are slightly positively skewed, suggesting that more observations fall below the mean. Conversely, TAXCRDIT, EXPOTEX, and INVESTALW are negatively skewed, meaning more values are concentrated above the mean. However, all skewness values remain within a small range, indicating an approximately symmetric distribution.

The kurtosis values for REVGGEN (3.43) and INVESTALW (3.57) suggest a distribution with slightly heavier tails than a normal distribution, while the kurtosis for TAXHOLI (2.25), TAXCRDIT (3.11), and EXPOTEX (3.04) indicate near-normal distributions. The Jarque-Bera test results confirm that all variables have probability values greater than 0.05, indicating no significant deviation from normality.

The sum values indicate that TAXCRDIT has the highest total (295), while INVESTALW has the lowest (273). Similarly, the sum of squared deviations is highest for TAXCRDIT (52.95) and lowest for INVESTALW (38.48), reflecting differences in variability. Each variable is based on 95 observations, ensuring sufficient data points for reliable analysis.

It is therefore means that on the average the five variables are approximately normally distributed with minimal deviations in skewness and kurtosis. The distribution of tax incentives appears to be relatively even, with tax credits showing slightly greater variability

Table 11: Correlation Analysis

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary
 Date: 03/15/25 Time: 02:30
 Sample: 1 95
 Included observations: 95

Correlation Probability	REVGGEN	TAXHOLI	TAXCRDIT	EXPOTEX	INVESTALW
REVGGEN	1.000000 -----				
TAXHOLI	-0.145465 0.1596	1.000000 -----			
TAXCRDIT	0.022074 0.8318	0.088460 0.3940	1.000000 -----		
EXPOTEX	0.031393 0.7627	-0.040002 0.7003	0.014702 0.8875	1.000000 -----	
INVESTALW	0.018124 0.8616	0.040190 0.6990	-0.082783 0.4251	-0.066061 0.5247	1.000000 -----

Source: Researchers compilation, 2025

The correlation matrix presents the relationships between Revenue Generation (REVGGEN), Tax Holidays (TAXHOLI), Tax Credit (TAXCRDIT), Export Expansion Grant (EXPOTEX), and Investment Allowance (INVESTALW). The correlation coefficients range from -1 to 1, where positive values indicate a direct relationship, negative values indicate an inverse relationship, and values close to zero suggest no strong association.

The correlation between REVGEN and TAXHOLI is -0.145, suggesting a weak negative relationship, meaning that tax holidays may not significantly contribute to revenue generation. However, the probability value (0.1596) indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant at conventional significance levels. The correlation between REVGEN and TAXCRDIT is 0.022, which is close to zero, indicating no meaningful association between tax credits and revenue generation. Similarly, the correlation between REVGEN and EXPOTEX (0.031) and REVGEN and INVESTALW (0.018) are also very low, suggesting no strong relationship between revenue generation and these incentives. The high probability values confirm that these correlations are not statistically significant.

Among the independent variables, TAXHOLI and TAXCRDIT have a correlation of 0.088, TAXHOLI and EXPOTEX have a correlation of -0.040, and TAXHOLI and INVESTALW have a correlation of 0.040, all of which are weak relationships with no statistical significance. Likewise, TAXCRDIT has a weak negative correlation with INVESTALW (-0.082) and EXPOTEX (0.014), suggesting that these incentives do not strongly interact.

Overall, the results indicate that there are no strong or statistically significant correlations between revenue generation and the tax incentives analyzed. This suggests that the impact of these incentives on revenue generation may not be straightforward and could require further analysis, possibly incorporating additional factors such as policy implementation and economic conditions.

Table 12: Regression Output
Dependent Variable: REVGEN

Method: Least Squares

Date: 01/19/26 Time: 20:46

Sample: 1 95

Included observations: 95

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.273402	0.346377	3.676350	0.0004
TAXHOLI	0.208830	0.107335	1.945588	0.0550
TAXCRDIT	0.252080	0.115465	2.183169	0.0318
EXPOTEX	-0.024208	0.053013	-0.456635	0.6491
INVESTALW	0.097204	0.015061	6.454108	0.0000
R-squared	0.213082	Mean dependent var		0.998243
Adjusted R-squared	0.119401	S.D. dependent var		0.353326
S.E. of regression	0.331562	Akaike info criterion		0.742554
Sum squared resid	9.234403	Schwarz criterion		1.038266
Log likelihood	-24.27132	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.862044
F-statistic	2.274558	Durbin-Watson stat		2.011955
Prob(F-statistic)	0.020696			

The regression analysis results provide insight into the relationship between RevGen (the dependent variable) and four independent variables: TaxHoli (Tax Holiday), TaxCrdit (Tax Credit), ExpotEx (Export Exemption), and InvestAlw (Investment Allowance). The model's R-squared value of 0.213 indicates that these independent variables together explain only 21.3% of the variation in RevGen. The Adjusted R-squared (0.119), which accounts for the number of predictors, suggests that after adjusting for model complexity, only 11.9% of the variation in RevGen is explained by the included variables. This relatively low R-squared value implies that other important factors influencing revenue generation are not captured by the current model.

Among the independent variables, Investment Allowance (InvestAlw) has the strongest and most significant impact on RevGen, with a coefficient of 0.0972 and a p-value of 0.0000 (less than 0.01), indicating a highly significant positive relationship. This suggests that an increase in Investment Allowance is strongly associated with an increase in RevGen. Tax Credit (TaxCrdit) is also statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.0318$), with a positive coefficient of 0.2521, meaning that higher tax credits are linked to increased RevGen. Tax Holiday (TaxHoli), on the other hand, has a p-value of 0.0550, making it marginally insignificant at the conventional 5% level but still close to significance. This suggests that while tax holidays might influence RevGen, the effect is not strong enough to be confidently confirmed in this sample. Export Exemption (ExpotEx) is the weakest predictor, with a p-value of 0.6491, indicating no significant impact on RevGen. This suggests that export exemptions do not meaningfully contribute to revenue generation and may not be necessary in the model.

The F-statistic of 2.27 ($p = 0.0207$) suggests that, overall, the model is statistically significant, meaning that at least one of the independent variables meaningfully predicts RevGen. However, the relatively low R-squared and the presence of an insignificant variable (ExpotEx) indicate that the model could be improved by removing weak predictors and possibly introducing other relevant factors. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.01 suggests no serious autocorrelation issues, meaning that residuals appear to be randomly distributed, which is a good sign for model validity.

4.2 Discussion of findings

This study examined the impact of tax incentives on revenue generation (RevGen) using multiple regression analysis. The independent variables considered were Tax Holiday (TaxHoli), Tax Credit (TaxCrdit), Export Exemption (ExpotEx), and Investment Allowance (InvestAlw). The regression results provided key insights into the significance and influence of these variables on revenue generation.

Among the independent variables, Investment Allowance (InvestAlw) showed the strongest and most significant effect on revenue generation, with a coefficient of 0.0972 and a p-value of 0.0000 (highly significant). This suggests that increasing investment allowance positively influences revenue generation. This finding is in line with the findings of Abiodun (2020).

Tax Credit (TaxCrdit) was also statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.0318$), indicating a meaningful positive effect. This is in line with the study of Efeeloo and Doonu (2020)

Conversely, Tax Holiday (TaxHoli) was marginally insignificant with a p-value of 0.0550, meaning its impact on revenue generation is not strong enough to be conclusively established. Export Exemption (ExpotEx) was found to be statistically insignificant ($p = 0.6491$) and does not contribute meaningfully to revenue generation.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that Investment Allowance and Tax Credit play a significant role in revenue generation, while Tax Holiday has a weak impact, and Export Exemption does not significantly influence revenue generation. The relatively low R-squared value suggests that other factors not included in this model may also contribute to revenue generation. Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Since Investment Allowance is the most significant factor influencing revenue generation, policymakers should consider expanding or modifying this incentive to encourage more investment and economic growth.
2. The study found that Tax Credit has a positive impact on revenue generation. Governments should ensure that tax credit policies remain attractive and effective in stimulating economic activities.
3. Given the marginal significance of Tax Holiday, policymakers should assess whether this incentive is effectively promoting business growth or if adjustments are needed to make it more impactful.
4. As Export Exemption was found to be statistically insignificant, it may not be an effective tool for increasing revenue generation. Instead, resources should be redirected towards more impactful tax incentives.

References

- Abdelhakim, N., & Zouaghi, L. (2022). The effect of taxation on financial performance: The case of Tunisian companies. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 1(1), 27-48.
- Abdulrahman, S., & Kabir, M. K. (2017). Tax incentive as a real modifier for industrial growth and development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Development Strategies in Humanities, Management and Social Sciences*, 7(1), 72-88.
- Adereti S.A., Adesina J.A., & Sanni M.R. (2011). who examined the impact of tax incentives on government revenue in Nigeria. *Journal of finance and taxation*, 2(1), 1-20.
- Ahanger, A. (2021). Influence of FDI characteristics on high-quality development of China's economy. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 2(8), 18977-18988.
- Abiodun, A. (2020). The Impact of Tax Collection and Incentives on Economic Growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Economics Research*, 9(4), 170-175.
- Bloom, N., Griffith, R., & Van Reenen, J. (2022). Do R&D tax credits work? Evidence from a panel of countries 1979-1997. *Journal of Public Economics*, 85(1), 1-31.
- Chen, L., & Yang, W. (2019). R&D tax credits and firm innovation: Evidence from China. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 146, 233-241.

- Dai, C., & Chapman, G. (2022). R&D tax incentives and innovation: Examining the role of programme design in China. *Technovation*, 113, 102-419.
- Dai, C., & Liu, Y. (2018). Comparative analysis of the influence of tax incentives and financial subsidies on enterprise R&D. *Economic Science*, 3, 58-71.
- Efeeloo N., & Doonu M. (2020). Revisiting Tax Exempts, Tax Credits and Operating Profits of Listed Firms in Nigeria. *Journal of accounting and financial management* 10(7),135-143
- Febrianti, A. M., & Jufri, N. S. N. (2022). Examining the predictors of enterprise performance: The role of transformational leadership, HRM digitalization, and organizational commitment. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 11(4), 131-139.
- Gabriel, E. D., & Ezekiel, A. I. (2019). The Nexus between Tax Revenue and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting*, 4 (2), 45-55
- Genschel, P., & Seelkopf, L. (2016). Did they learn to tax? Taxation trends outside the OECD. *Review of International Political Economy*, 23(2), 316-344.
- Ghazinoory, S., & Hashemi, Z. (2020). Do tax incentives and direct funding enhance innovation input and output in high-tech enterprises? *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 32(4), 100-394.
- González-Rodríguez, M. R., Diaz-Fernandez, M. C., Shi, F., & Okumus, F. (2021). Exploring the links among corporate social responsibility, reputation, and performance from a multidimensional perspective. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 99, (10), 30-47.
- Hofman, B. (2018). Reflections on 40 years of China's reforms. In R. Garnaut, L. Song, & F. Cai (Eds.), *China's 40 Years of Reform and Development* (pp. 53-66). ANU Press.
- Huang, N., & Liu, Y. (2024). Structural tax reduction, financing constraint relief and enterprise innovation efficiency. *Finance Research Letters*, 60, 104848.
- Imran, M., & Rehman, Z. U. (2024). Interplay of government support and foreign investment in enhancing R&D in China's strategic sectors. *Journal of Organizational Technology and Entrepreneurship*, 2(1), 1-13.
- Lee, M., & Huang, Y. L. (2020). Corporate social responsibility and enterprise performance: A hybrid text mining algorithm. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3075.
- Millot, V., Johansson, Å., Sorbe, S., & Turban, S. (2020). Corporate taxation and investment of multinational firms: Evidence from firm-level data (*OECD Taxation Working Paper No. 51*).

- Manir, U., & Zubairu, M. S. (2026). Evaluating the Impact of Tax Incentives on Revenue Generation: Evidence from the Nigeria Revenue Service. *AKSU Journal of Social Sciences* 1(1), 282-291.
- Nnubia, I. C., & Obiora, F. C. (2018). Effect of tax incentives on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Conflict Management*, 3(2), 142–160.
- Oguttu, A. W. (2018). International tax competition, harmful tax practices, and the “race to the bottom”: A special focus on strategic tax incentives in Africa. *Comparative and International Law Journal of Southern Africa*, 51(3), 293–319.
- Okeke, M. N., Mbonu, C. M., & Ndubuisi, A. N. (2018). Tax revenue and economic development in Nigeria: A disaggregated analysis. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management*, 8(2), 178–199.
- Okoth, E. (2023). Effects of tax incentives and subsidies on economic growth in developing economies. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, VII(VII). <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS>
- Olowo, S. O., Anisere-Hammed, R. A., & Adewole, A. O. (2020). Effect of tax incentives on the growth and development of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research*, 3(1), 77–84.
- Sebele-Mpofu, F. Y., Gomera, D., & Sibanda, B. (2022). Tax incentives: A panacea or problem to enhancing economic growth in developing countries. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 8(2), 90–123. <https://doi.org/10.32602/jafas.2022.012>
- Siyanbola, T., Adedeji, B., & Rahman, M. M. (2017). Measuring the level of women work burnout and sustainable remedial measures in garments industry of Bangladesh: Human resource accounting: A panacea for financial reporting problems in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, 7(2).
- Soon, A. L., Derashid, C., & Bidin, Z. (2020). DTPB as a better voluntary tax compliance predictor—A comparison study. *Journal of Business Management and Accounting*, 10(2), 31–56.
- Supriyati, I. H. (2021). Tax avoidance, tax incentives, and tax compliance during the COVID-19 pandemic: Individual knowledge perspectives. *Journal of Accounting and Strategic Finance*, 4(2), 222–241.
- Tapang, A. T., Onodi, B. E., & Amaraihu, A. H. (2018). Effect of tax incentives on foreign direct investment in the petroleum industry in Nigeria. *IIARD International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 4(7), 30-39.
- Tijjani, H., Ibrahim, A. S., Ardo, A. M., & Yusuf, A. U. (2023). The impact of forensic accounting on taxpayer attitude and compliance towards tax evasion within SMEs in North East Nigeria. *Journal of Business Management and Accounting*, 13(1), 79–105. <https://doi.org/10.32890/jbma2023.13.1.4>

- Tilahun, M. (2019). Determinants of tax compliance: A systematic review. *Economics*, 8(1), 1–7.
- Ugwu, C. C., Okwa, I. E., & Inyang, E. E. (2020). Tax incentives and investment growth: The Nigerian perspective. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 3(1).
- Ugwu, J. I. (2018). Tax incentives and foreign direct investment (FDI): Implication for export promotion in Nigeria, Ghana, and South Africa, post-IFRS adoption. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 6(9), 31–52.
- Vincent, O. (2021). The development of a scale to measure SMEs' tax compliance in Nigeria: An adaptation of Fischer's model. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation*, 13(3), 132–143.
- Zolt, E. M. (2013). Tax incentives and tax base protection issues (*Draft Paper No. 3*). *Papers on Selected Topics in Protecting the Tax Base of Developing Countries*. United Nations. https://www.un.org/esa/ffd/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/20140604_Paper3_Zolt.pdf